

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-2-245-IBN-5-1% rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	16	Acq. Method Set:	1%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 2 245
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	7/15/2022 10:07:30 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 19:36:34 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	10.461	8907639	49.67	575861
2	11.570	9025751	50.33	525784

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-279-IBN-5-1% ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	29	Acq. Method Set:	1%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 279
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/11/2023 10:43:04 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/17/2023 4:19:02 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	10.558	6493084	97.48	359694
2	11.806	167690	2.52	9968